

PERFORMANCE EVALUATION OF VARIOUS DATA MINING CLASSIFICATION TECHNIQUES THAT CORRECTLY CLASSIFY BANKING TRANSACTION AS FRAUDULENT

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Abstract— Data mining is a sum of process to find anomalies, patterns, correlations which can assist banks to look for hidden patterns in a group and discover unknown relationship in the data. In this competitive world, governments, private companies, large organizations and all businesses, predict their future plans using various methods of data mining. Banks are an integral part of a country's economy, contributing to both people and governments. In case of money transaction bank is the most essential media in our country. In this circumstance, some vested peoples gratify their evil task. These individual acts make a big issue for our country's economy. In this paper, we have discussed about the comparative study on several data mining classification techniques that are generally used to classify suspicious transactions, included Naïve Bayes, MLP (is the particular feed forward method of ANN), sequential minimal optimization (SMO) and decision tree based J48 & random forest algorithm. we have found the random forest algorithm performance is better than others to classify banking transactions.

Index Terms— Banking Dataset, Retail Banking Sector, Data Mining, Classification Techniques, Suspicious Transaction detection

I. INTRODUCTION

Currently, huge electronic data repositories are being maintained by banks and other financial institutions, where most valuable and precious data bits are embedded with this repository. To handle this huge number of data and make them ease for finding the analytical pattern, data mining is one of the best approaches. Now a day, the modes of

payment methods are changed into online transactions. Banking system provides different type of payment facilities like internet banking, e-services, e-commerce, and card payments for improving online transaction. Using this blessing way, some peoples of vested interest in our country as well as all over the world gratified their evil task. They transact black money as well as the unaccountable money goes to be accountable. In order to hide their serious financial amounts, they transact over limited transaction, pretending their business transaction. Some businesses have been known to use fraudulent bookkeeping to overstate sales and income. These individual fraudulent transactions act a big issue in the economy of our country. These individual suspect transactions act a big issue in the economy of our country. These fraudulent transactions should be strictly prohibited for the development of our country's economic future. For the solution of finding the suspect transactional account we are motivated to do this work by gathering knowledge of data mining and machine learning. Our main objective is analyzing and identifying the best technique according to their performance to classify suspect transactions more correctly.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW AND AIM

This paper deals with banking fraud detection by identifying the suspect transaction. This is quite confidential and challenging job for using dataset. In previous year some work has been done on several fraud detections. In paper [1], neural networks-based outlier detection methods are used to detection credit card-based fraud detection. Outlier detection is an observation of unsupervised learning dataset to identify the suspicious transaction. On the other hand, in neural network the connected graph found the decision by combining the unsupervised or supervised method. A parallel Granular neural networks (GNN) method uses fuzzy neural networks and rule-based approach. By combing these techniques together neural network increases its statistical model to reduce the number of false rejections [1]. An intrusion detection system is needed to automate and perform system monitoring by keeping aggregate audit trail statistics. The computer intrusion detection performs

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by categorizing two broad section of misuse and anomaly detection. For this detection Expert system, model-based reasoning and neural network methods are used [1]. Beside these above stated techniques, the clustering with slope, Hash table techniques, k-means clustering, genetic algorithm and hidden Markov model-based techniques are used in several times for the specific datasets [2, 3]. Reviewing the all used models and techniques the conclusion is blurry about the different size and different characters of datasets. For being increasing the banking dependency, the fraud operation is increased in following line. So, the aim will be to identifying the best techniques to find the suspicious transaction [3].

Some names of suspicious activities, which took place in Bangladeshi banking sector previous years. These activities are well known as banking fraud:

- a. Crimes by individuals against consumers, clients or other business people [4].
- b. Employee fraud against employers. For example, payroll fraud; falsifying expense claims; thefts of cash, assets or intellectual property (IP); false accounting [4].
- c. Crimes by businesses against investors, consumers and employees, e.g. financial statement fraud.
- d. Crimes against financial institutions, e.g. using lost and stolen credit cards; cheque frauds; fraudulent insurance claims [4].
- e. Crimes by individuals or businesses against government, e.g. grant fraud; tax evasion; over transaction [4].
- f. Crimes by professional criminals against major organizations, i.e. major counterfeiting rings; mortgage frauds; identity fraud; money laundering [4].

A research has been done for mining fraud using data mining techniques. Here the Apriori algorithm is used to replace the clustering algorithm. This algorithm helps to detect fraudster behavior easily [5]. *Ch. Suresh et al.* proposed a new hybrid approach to identify the transactional fraud to prevent the money laundering in Indian banking sector [6].

III. PROPOSED METHOD

In this work, our main task is to evaluate the results of the various techniques that identify those transactions which conducting as suspicious. The model depicts selection, followed by pre-processing, transforming, data mining and finally interpreting and evaluating, are the stage of classifying suspect transaction.

Fig 1: Block diagram of the proposed method.

For evaluating these algorithms at first, we need the dataset. Due to the high confidentiality of banking transaction data and no permission to disclose these as public, some limitations should be maintaining in the case of testing. Testing tools should be more secure. Bank has limitation to provide this data for test so, before starting data preparation phase it's required to have transactions simulator that responsible for simulate transactions and prepare imbalanced data set. Data Pre-processing would be required after dataset formulation as follows:

- a. Refine data by Remove the transactions corresponding to those customers who have only one transaction in dataset
- b. Segregate transactions into legal and fraud transactions. The refined imbalanced data attributes represented in table 1.

TABLE 1: THE BANKING TRANSACTIONAL DATASET ATTRIBUTES.

No	Attribute Name	Type
1	Account Number	Nominal
2	Transaction-frequency limit / month	Real
3	Transaction-amount limit / month	Real
4	Max-transaction limit / month	Real
5	Transaction-frequency occurred	Real
6	Transaction-amount occurred	Real
7	Max-transaction occurred	Real
8	Status	Nominal (suspect / not-suspect)

The datasets are stated in eight attributes. First one is the account number. To maintain the confidentiality, it depicts the demo numbers. Next three columns represent the limitation of the account which is the main indicators to classify is that transaction fraudulent or not. Next three attributes show the occurred information for the accountants. Finally, we have to add the last result attribute, which will contain the predicting result named status.

IV. BACKGROUND

We will discuss about the Naïve Bayes, MLP, SMO, decision tree-based algorithm. Here MLP is an ANN driven particular feed forward technique. For statistical measurement with probability we can use Bayes algorithm. Bayes theorem provides a way of calculating posterior probability $P(c/x)$ from $P(c)$, $P(x)$ and $P(x/c)$. It looks like the equation below:

$$P(c/x) = \frac{P(x|c)P(c)}{P(x)}$$

$$P(c/X) = P(x_1/c) \times P(x_2/c) \times \dots \times P(x_n/c) \times P(c) \tag{1}$$

Where, $P(c/x)$ is the posterior probability of class (c, target) given predictor (x, attributes). $P(c)$ is the prior probability of class. $P(x/c)$ is the likelihood which is the probability of predictor given class. $P(x)$ is the prior probability of predictor. As well as for neural network algorithm we will use the MLP techniques [6]. An MLP consists of at least three layers of nodes. Except for the input nodes, each node is a neuron that uses a nonlinear activation function. MLP utilize the supervised learning techniques. Perceptron learning algorithm is essentially doing same thing find a linear separator by adjusting weights on misclassified examples. Unlike perceptron, SMO has to maintain sum over examples of example weight Ames example label. Therefore, when SMO adjusts weight of one example, it must also adjust weight of another.

We can view weight vector for perceptron as weighted sum of examples [10]:

$$(w1, w2 \dots wN) = a1 (x 1 1, x 1 2 \dots x 1 N) + a2 (x 2 1, x 2 2 \dots x 2 N) + \dots + aM (x M 1, x M 2 \dots x M N) \tag{2}$$

And finally, we will use the decision tree based J48 & random forest algorithm. A predictive machine learning model which decides the target value of a new sample based on different attribute values of the available data is J48 decision tree. The different attributes denote by the internal nodes of a decision tree, the branches between the nodes tell us the possible values that these attributes can have in the experimental samples, while the terminal nodes tell us the final value of the dependent variable [11]. As well as random forest is the type of the decision tree-based algorithm. Random forests are an ensemble learning method for classification, regression and other tasks

that operate by constructing a multitude of decision trees at training time and outputting the class, that is the mode of the classification or mean prediction of the individual trees. This comes at the expense of a small increase and some loss of interpretability, but generally greatly boosts the presentation of the final model.

Decision tree is the most popular model for classifying datasets. A decision tree is a tree like graph representing the relationships between a set of variables. Decision tree models are used to solve classification and prediction problems where instances are classified into one of two classes, typically positive and negative, or churner and non-churner in the churn classification case [12].

V. IMPLEMENTATION AND RESULTS

To do this task, we collected the legal transactional datasets form Bangladesh retail bank (IBBL). We performed several activities include varying the attribute, percentage splitting and random seed splitting on the collected datasets. For percentage splitting 85.5% of training data is used. Table 2 along with figure 2 represents the evaluations of the Naïve Bayes, MLP, SMO and decision tree based J48 & random forest algorithm.

TABLE 2 (A): PERCENTAGE SPLITTING RESULT OF NAÏVE BAYES ALGORITHM.

Seed Values	Correctly Classified Instance	Incorrectly Classified Instance
1	78%	22%
2	88%	12%
3	83%	17%
4	84%	16%

Table 2 (a) shows the accuracy level of identification of classifying in random seed splitting. For value 2, we got the better result as 88% of correctly classified instance.

As well as in ANN driven Multilayer Perceptron algorithm, at least three layers are required where first and last layer will be input and output layer respectively. The results of MLP algorithm using percentage splitting are shown in table 2 (b). When the value is 3, we got the better result as 95% of correctly classified instance.

TABLE 2 (B): MLP DATA ANALYSIS RESULT IN PERCENTAGE.

Seed Values	Correctly Classified Instance	Incorrectly Classified Instance
1	88%	12%
2	91%	9%
3	95%	5%
4	90%	10%

Support vector machine-based SMO algorithm gives too close result as MLP as shown in Table 2 (c).

TABLE 2 (C): SMO PERCENTAGE SPLITTING TEST RESULT.

Seed Values	Correctly Classified Instance	Incorrectly Classified Instance
1	66%	34%
2	90%	10%
3	84%	16%
4	81%	19%

In percentage splitting methods, using decision tree based J48 algorithm the result is more accurate than others. This is JAVA driven C4.5 statistical algorithms. Table 2 (d) depicts the result.

TABLE 2 (D): J48 PERCENTAGE SPLITTING TEST RESULT.

Seed Values	Correctly Classified Instance	Incorrectly Classified Instance
1	95%	6%
2	93%	7%
3	86%	14%
4	92%	8%

As well as, the random forest tree algorithm shows the best performance to identify the transactional data. Random forests or random decision forests are an ensemble learning method for classification, regression and other tasks, that operate by constructing a multitude of decision trees at training time and outputting the class that is the mode of the classes (classification) or mean prediction (regression) of the individual trees. Table 2 (e) shows the result.

TABLE 2 (E): PERCENTAGE SPLITTING RESULTS OF RANDOM FOREST TREE.

Seed Value	Correctly Classified Instance	Incorrectly Classified Instance
1	97%	3%
2	98%	2%
3	93%	7%
4	95%	5%

The accuracy level of identification of classifying in random seed splitting is the best. At the point when value is 2, found the better result as 98% of correctly classified instance. Moreover, in the cross-validation test, all algorithms performed with significantly. The analysis result is shown in the table 3.

TABLE 3: CROSS VALIDATION RESULT OF FIVE ALGORITHMS.

No	Algorithm	Correctly classified	Incorrectly classified
1	Naïve Bayes	79%	21%
2	MLP	90%	10%
3	SMO	80%	20%
4	J48	92%	8%
5	Random Forest	96%	4%

Fig 2: Graphical representation of percentage splitting with 85.5%.

Analyzing these algorithms to detect fraudulent transaction with a banking dataset using different seed splitting on percentage splitting method, we got some statistical information to reach in a distinct point. The decision tree based random forest is the best approaches for detecting most accurate classification process. In fig-2 the blue bar shows the correctly classified result and the red shows the incorrectly classified result. Here the decision tree based random forest algorithm is perform as 96% accurate to classify the transactional data. For banking dataset decision tree will be the perfect method to identify the suspicious transaction. In both supervised and unsupervised method.

VI. CONCLUSION

In conclusion of this paper, a comparative study on different data mining techniques used for fraud detection has been introduced. Random forest algorithm is used to extract vital information from existing huge amount of data. Here random forest's prediction is most efficient and this comparative statistical paper will obtain huge benefit and derive considerable competitive advantage for future contribution.

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